

INDUCTIVE TEACHING GRAMMAR FOR ENTERMEDIATE LEVEL

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The artical: is indructive teaching grammar for entermidiate level and it gives about information grammar B2 levels for pupils.

Inductive teaching is a method for to teache students . This method contrast with the deductive method. Inductive instruction makes use of student “noticing”. Instead of explaining a given concept and following this explanation with examples, the teacher presents students with many examples showing how the concept is used. The intent is for students to “notes”, by way of examples. Inductive learning can be more time –and energy- consuming and more determining of the teacher and the learners. It is also possible that during the proses, the learner may arrive at incorrect inference or produce ancorrect or incomplete rule. Also, an inductive approach may frustrate learners whose personal learning style and or/past learning experience is more in line with being tought via a more teacher- centeredand deductive approach.

Theteacher draws pupils’ attention to the new element in the form of a rule, a very short one. It is usually done in the mother tongue. Forexample: Помни, что во множественном числе к существетельному прибавляется окончание –s [s,z] или –is [Iz]. Or: Помни, что во трицательных предложениях ставится вспомогательный глагол “do not” (“does not”).The rule helps the learner to understand and to assimilate the structural meaning of the elements. It ensures a conscious approach to learning. This approach provides favourable conditions for the speedy development of correct and more flexible language use. However it does not mean that the teacher should ask pupils to say this or that rule, Rules do not ensure the mastery of the language. They only help to attain the practical goal. If a pupil can recognize and employ correctly the forms that are appropriate, that is

sufficient. When the learner can give ample proof of these abilities we may say that he has fulfilled the syllabus requirements. If learner has acquired such a mechanism, he can produce correct sentences in a foreign language. Paul Roberts writes: “Grammar is something that produces the sentences of a language. By something we mean a speaker of English.¹ If you speak English natively, you have built into you rules of English grammar. In a sense, you are an English grammar. You possess, as an essential part of your being, a very complicated apparatus which enables you to produce infinitely many sentences, all English ones, including many that you have never specifically learned. Furthermore by applying you rule you can easily tell whether a sentence that you hear a grammatical English sentence or not.

A command of English as is envisaged by the school syllabus cannot be ensured without the study of grammar. Pupils need grammar to be able to aud, speak, read, and write in the target language. Before speaking about the selection of grammar material it is necessary to consider the concept “grammar”, i.e., what it meant by “grammar”. By grammar one can mean adequate comprehension and correct usage of words in the act of communication, that is, intuitive knowledge of the grammar of the language. It is a set of reflexes enabling a person to communicate with his associates. Such knowledge is acquired by a child in the mother tongue before he goes to schools.²

This “grammar” functions without the individual’s awareness of technical nomenclature; in other words, he has no idea of the system of the language, and to use all the word-endings for singular and plural, for tense, and all the other grammar rules without special grammar lessons only due to the abundance of auding and speaking. His young mind grasps the facts and “makes simple grammar rules” for arranging the words to express carious thoughts and feelings. This is true because sometimes little children make mistakes by using a common rule for words to which that rule cannot be applied.

By “grammar” we also mean the system of the language, the discovery and description of the nature of language itself. It is not a natural grammar, but a constructed one. There are several *constructed grammars: traditional, structural, and transformational grammars*. Traditional grammar studies the forms of words (morphology) and how they are put together in sentences (syntax); structural grammar studies structures of various levels of the language (morpheme level) and syntactic level; transformational grammar studies basic structures and

¹Jiang, X. The Effect of Integrating Inductive Approach and Deductive Approach with Multimedia Assistance Into Acquisition of Subjunctive Mood. *Sino-US English Teaching*, 9(9), 2012

²Jack Umstatter, J. *The Grammar Teachers’ Activity a- Day 180*. USA: Jossey – Bass 2010.

transformation rules.

Another study by Alzubi (2015) was also conducted to study the effectiveness of inductive and methods in teaching English grammar. The study also attempted to see which of these two methods had a positive effect on the grammar achievement of university students and elementary school students in Jordan. 180 students were sampled for the study. Eighty were first year university English students and the rest were elementary stage students. The participants of the study consisted of four assigned sections. The relevant pre-tests were administered to the students of both groups at each stage (university and school) to make sure that the groups were equivalent at the time of starting the experiment. The researcher designed two grammar achievement tests as the instruments of this study. The instrument of each stage consists of two achievement tests (pre- test and post-test). The results showed a significant difference in favour of the inductive way of teaching. Hence, the inductive teaching approach was more efficient than the teaching approach. The study however did not focus on broader aspects of syntax in grammar but was limited in this vein. The current study fills this gap by looking at a variety of grammar rules so as to offer a broader view on the best approach to be used to teach grammar in general.³

Inductive teaching is learner – centred and help promote effective learning. It has the guarantee to reading grammar textbooks in class. Instead they should take pupils through a lot of activities to make grammar lessons interesting. Professionally trained teachers of English language should influence the teaching of the subject in their schools through the engagement with other class teachers. Mistakes from students” essays should be discussed with them. This activity should help students solve their grammatical problems. In the language classroom it is expected that students are to acquire knowledge and apply it without difficulty but in the case of grammar, knowledge acquired is not being applied effectively. The mistakes some students make in their oral language and written essays attest to this fact. There is the need to handle teaching and learning of grammar in such a way that students will be able to acquire the knowledge and use it effectively.

THE LIST OF USE LITERATURE:

³Dykes, B. Grammar for everyone Practical tools for learning and teaching grammar. Australia: Acer press. Columbia, Ohio State University Press

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1. Jiang, X. The Effect of Integrating Inductive Approach and Deductive Approach with Multimedia Assistance Into Acquisition of Subjunctive Mood. Sino-US English Teaching, 9(9), 2012
 2. Jack Umstatter, J. The Grammar Teachers" Activity a- Day 180.USA: Jossey – Bass 2010.
 - 3 Dykes, B. Grammar for everyone Practical tools for learning and teaching grammar. Australia: Acer press. Columbia, Ohio State University Press

